

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Measuring social and psychological factors through home-study setting towards improved academic performance

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Abstract

This study determined the relationship among social and psychological factors through home -study setting of Grades 6 pupils in Liciada Elementary School, in Bustos, Bulacan during the first quarter of School Year 2022-2023. The main objective is to find the implications of social and psychological factors on the achievement of pupils and finding benefits of home-study setting. The method used in the study was t-test and pearson (r). Using descriptive correlational research as research design in the total population of 167 Grade 6 pupils as respondents of the study, the answers to the problems raised in this study were summarized as follows: The number of siblings and socio-economic status has a significant relationship between pupils' demographic profile and social factor in home study setting with p-values 0.011 and 0.000 which is less than the level of significance at 0.05. Social factor in home-study setting and respondents' academic achievement has a significant relationship with p-value of 0.001 which was less than the level of significance at 0.05. On the other hand, psychological factor in home study setting and respondents' academic achievement has no significant relationship with p-value 0.220 which was greater than the level of significance at 0.05. The pupil's achievement on this present research will be useful to the parents and policymakers in finding the benefits, policy framing, and advantages of home-study.

Keywords: Social Factors; Psychological Factors; Social influence; Social Presence; Sense of Self Efficacy; Academic Achievement

1. Introduction

Schools have no worth without teachers and pupils. These two groups were by and at large the most important assets for any academic institute. The connection between the two groups and academic institution was the performance, in which without pupils' performance there would be no progress or achievement noted for both the teachers and an academic institution. Hence, it is an important factor in any academic institution.

Pupils' performance in academic has received the attention of many researchers around the globe for many decades. It is one of most challenging aspects in many academic literatures because their performance has been affected by academic, social, psychological, economic, and environmental cohesion (Alani, Farooq & Hawas, Abdulrazzaq, 2021).

In the Philippines, home study setting was not being given too much attention by parents because for some parents, education remains in school and learning should be given by the teachers inside the four corners of the classroom. Follow ups were seldomly given because aside from parents were busy to their work, they were expecting that pupils learned the competencies they need in school. Teachers communicate with parents if the pupils really need remediation at home. Parental involvement has been linked to higher grades, improved test scores, and increased graduation rates. In our country, however, parental involvement in education was often limited to financial support. A study by the Asian

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Development Bank found that only 22% of Filipino parents were involved in their child's schooling, compared to the regional average of 38%. In another study of low-income Filipino parents, only 42% believed education was necessary for their child's future success. This highlights the need for schools to communicate the importance of education to parents better (Llego, 2022).

During elementary years, children's imaginative thinking develops rapidly, abstract thinking was gradually developed, and it was a critical period for the development of social-emotional competence. Social-psychological competence predicts a variety of developmental outcomes, including academic achievement, psychological development, and interpersonal relationships. In the academic achievement section, children's learning occurs through hands-on inquiry and interaction with the external environment, and its effectiveness depends not only on the child's intellectual level, but non-intellectual factors also play an important role (Abrahams et al., 2019).

Social-psychological competence was a core competency for children's adaptation and social development in complex situations and plays an important role in children's overall development. In recent years, there has been an increased interest in identifying factors that may be related to growth in this set of skills, particularly during the elementary years when rapid development in social-psychological competence is most evident. The home learning environment, as an effective combination of activities and resources at home, is a major factor in the development of children's social-psychological competence (Lehrl et al., 2020).

Previous studies have shown that factors such as social influence, presence, support, identity and interaction affect the development of young children's social-psychological competence. However, the home learning environment was greater than just the sum of its component environmental elements (Juan et al., 2020).

Psychological competence theory suggested that emotions influence the direction of attention, the processes of memory, and problem-solving. Social-psychological competence, based on theories such as emotional intelligence, was the characteristic and behavior of individuals who established and maintained positive relationships with others, fulfilled the demands of the social environment, and achieved desired goals in groups. It included sense of self efficacy, extrinsic motivation, stress level which are important aspects of psychological factors that affect home study learning. Among these, sense of self-efficacy refers to the children's ability to respond according to the goal or task, preserved the goal when distractions are encountered, and inhibited habitual responses or impulsive behavior. Extrinsic motivation was the ability to make a distinction between internal feelings and external emotional expressions without violating the rules of emotional expression. Intrinsic motivation refers to children's ability to understand the emotions and intentions of others. Emotional regulation was the ability of children to induce, inhibit and maintain different emotional states. In general, these social and psychological factors do not operate in isolation. For example, children who are more able to regulate their own emotions, understand the perspectives of others, and express their emotions in socially acceptable ways are also more likely to maintain relationships and manage conflict (Silke et al., 2018).

School year 2020-2021 and 2021-2022 has been very challenging especially because of the pandemic. Teachers, Administrators and DepEd Officials found light on how would they manage providing quality education to our pupils. In line with this, DepEd released Order No. 12 entitled "Adoption of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan for School Year 2020-2021 in Light of the COVID-19 Public Health Emergency" which elaborated a detailed view on how to incorporate education in spite of the hazardous situation. DepEd has adopted different methods in teaching students due to Covid pandemic. They were called distance learning modalities. These were divided into three categories which was: Modular distance learning, Online distance learning and TV/Radio-based Instruction. Modular distance learning is a learning method where pupils learn using the printed self-learning modules or access digitally through electronic devices such as laptops, computers, and smartphones. (Yes, 2021)

In the recent Learning Recovery Plan (LRP) presentation of SDO Bulacan 2022-2024, a chunk of decreased among the number of numerates showed totally downward trend in the results of Reading Assessments for English and Filipino Grades 1-3, Project AN, Academic Proficiency Level in Science, NAT Grades 6 and 10 (National, Regional, Division), and PISA Simulation in pre-pandemic and during pandemic. Out-of-school youth (OSY) numbers have grown due to the impact of the pandemic on education.

Liciada Elementary School, one of the schools in Bustos District that have 86.22% of purely modular enrollees, conducted Continuous Improvement Project (CIP) entitled "Project PASADo; Planuhin, Alamin at Solusyunan Ang Dropout", that aimed to know the factors which triggers pupils to nearly had drop-out during the school year 2021-2022. Reasons such as; unclaimed modules because parents are busy at work, followed by family and health problems, low academic grades, and uncomfortable learning environment got the highest percentage among the factors.

The development of greater self-study or study skills was one of the advantages of home-study setting. Pupils take an active part in learning the subject's fundamentals. They have gained a sense of accountability by accomplishing the lessons. Enhancing learning on their own, with little or no assistance from others.

The teacher was capable of keeping track of the students' performance. Pupils could communicate with the teacher via e-mail, text message, or messenger chat. If at all possible, the teacher communicated with the children's parents and guardians who needed remediation or assistance at home. This was where the challenges come through. Children who has fulltime working parents experience difficulties in helping their children cope up with the distance learning. Some hired private tutors who could teach their children at home and guide them in learning. Home study setting has not been a thing in the Philippines because pupils learned lessons inside the classroom with just little follow up at home. This was the best time that home-study setting should be encouraged at school and at home.

Thus, the researcher was prompted to delve into measuring social and psychological factors through home-study setting towards improve academic performance.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

This study determined the relationship between the social and psychological factors of home-study setting to Grade 6 pupils' academic performance in Liciada Elementary School in Bustos, Bulacan during the 1st Quarter of School Year 2022-2023.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

- How may the demographic profile of the pupils be described in terms of:
 - Sex;
 - Number of siblings;
 - Socioeconomic status; and
 - Parents educational background?
- How may the social factors in home study setting be described in terms of:
 - Social influence;
 - Social presence;
 - Social space;
 - Social support;
 - Social identity; and
 - Social interaction?
- How may the psychological factors through home study setting be described in terms of:
 - Sense of self-efficacy;
 - Test anxiety;
 - Intrinsic motivation;
 - Extrinsic motivation; and
 - Stress level?
- How may the academic achievement of the pupils be described in terms of General Weighted Average (GWA) in 1st Quarter of SY 2022-2023?
- Is there a significant difference among demographic profile, social and psychological factors in home study setting?
- Is there a significant relationship among social and psychological factors in home study setting, and pupils' academic achievement?
- What program of activities can be crafted from the results of the study?

1.2. Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested in this study

- There is no significant difference among demographic profile, social and psychological factors in home study setting of respondents.

- There is no significant relationship among social and psychological factors of home study setting and Grade 6 pupils' academic performance.

1.3. Conceptual Framework

Home study setting could be related to the following social and psychological theories namely: Social Learning Theory and Cognitive Constructivism Theory

Albert Bandura's Social Learning Theory (SLT) is often described as an intermediate between behaviorism (traditional learning theory) and cognitive theory. Behaviorism focuses on one particular view of learning: a change in external behavior achieved through the use of reinforcement and repetition to shape behavior which relates to rote learning. Cognitive learning theory advocates that the different processes concerning learning can be explained by analyzing the mental processes. Thus, SLT is a bridge between behaviorism and cognitive approach (Rumjaun, A., Narod, F. 2020).

The basis of social learning theory was simple: People learned by watching other people. We can learn from anyone—teachers, parents, siblings, peers, co-workers, YouTube influencers, athletes, and even celebrities. We observed their behavior and we mimic that behavior. In short, we do what they do. The environment played a large part in learning. We model the behavior of the people around us, especially if we found these models similar to ourselves or if we want to emulate them.

From a psychological perspective to real-world exposure in the fields of social work and education, social learning has proven to be an effective tool for understanding the behavior, interactions, and attitudes of children. Social learning has also helped us to observe how cognitive and environmental factors contribute to learning and behavior.

A social constructivist learning environment incorporated the idea that deep learning (or implied as internal change, internalization of knowledge) occurs when students are actively engaged in the learning process and collaborate with other students (and stakeholders) to accomplish a shared goal. Research stated that these changes witnessed in the use of social media as part of higher education, have actually occurred in tandem with fundamental changes in pedagogical paradigms and learning theories, now embedded as part of constructivism theory. Although research on the effectiveness of social media for teaching-learning purposes is still in infancy, it is becoming more apparent that social media (some studies specifically referring to Facebook) as a social networking tool has the potential to be a transformational technique for learning, especially within higher education (Garcia et al., 2019)

Social factors had a significant role in cognitive development among children. Children live with their own parents, and they interact with their peers and teachers; all of these have a great deal of influence on a child's level of thinking and understanding to account for social factors and cultural contexts in cognitive development studies (Babakr, et al., 2019)

Furthermore, it explains that while some aspects of pupils learning can be attributed to individual differences and the impact of external experiences, other forms of learning are attributed to the pupils' interactions with those individuals outside of the home environment (Barry, 2019).

Piaget's Cognitive Constructivism Theory, which claims that the development of intelligence is an adaptation between an organism and its environment, is the theoretical framework on which this research was based. Piaget's theory of cognitive development proposes that humans cannot be given information that is immediately understood; rather, they must construct their own knowledge through four stages of learning: Sensorimotor stage, preoperational stage, concrete operational stage, and the formal operational stage (Piaget & Cook, 1952 cited in Auger et al., 2020).

Cognitivist teaching methods aimed to assist pupils in assimilating new information to existing knowledge, as well as enabling them to make the appropriate modifications to their existing intellectual framework to accommodate that information thus socialization from peer has a great influence on one's cognitive learning.

In a journal entitled, "Cognitive Challenges of Effective Teaching", it is stated that students who use ineffective study strategies may fail to acquire the prior knowledge they need to benefit from class lectures and assignments, which in turn may affect their mental mindset and influence them to believe they lack the ability needed to learn in the course. (Chew, S. L., & Cerbin, W. J., 2021).

Unlike behaviorist learning theory, where learners were thought to be motivated by extrinsic factors such as rewards and punishment, cognitive learning theory sees motivation as largely intrinsic. Because it involves significant restructuring of existing cognitive structures, successful learning requires a major personal investment on the part of

the learner. Learners must face up to the limitations of their existing knowledge and accept the need to modify or abandon existing beliefs. Without some kind of internal drive on the part of the learner to do so, external rewards and punishments such as grades are unlikely to be sufficient.

Different researchers sorted study practices in various ways, and there are many common elements in this variety. It sorted studying as making the plan (going to the class on time, ability to adapt to changing conditions, being flexible, being decisive in applying the prepared studying plan), studying environment (the importance of the place saved for studying, lighting the room adequately), concentration (eliminating distracting items on the desk, starting to study without losing time as soon as one sits on the chair, changing the studying technique to increase concentration if necessary), learning (ability to identify the important points, goal-setting), reading (conceptual reading, reading graphs-tables-figures), note-taking (choosing main-points, studying notes again), answering questions (being calm before the exam imagining the questions, taking time to understand), and receiving teacher support (Berstein, 2021).

According to Kumar, students with good study habits get higher grades. The results of studies have shown that students' possession of study habits help them have high motivation for learning, take more time to learn, have positive attitudes towards learning and feel more successful (Kumar, 2019).

Social factors have had a significant role in cognitive development among children. Children live with their own parents, and they interact with their peers and teachers; all of these have a great deal of influence on a child's level of thinking and understanding (Cacioppo et al., 2013). Russian psychologist, Lev Vygotsky proposed that children's minds develop in a sociocultural context rather than interactions with a physical object which Piaget suggested (Schacter, Gilbert, & Wegner, 2011). Thus, it is suggested for psychological researchers to account for social factors and cultural contexts in cognitive development studies. Piaget believes that children between the ages of 2 and 7 are in the preoperative period where they do not yet grasp concrete reasoning, are unable to control knowledge, and are unable to take the point of view of other persons, which he called egocentrism (McLeod, 2018). Children are also increasingly skilled at using symbols during the preoperative process, as shown by the rise in playing and pretending.

Children from birth to around 2 years of age, meanwhile, are in the sensorimotor stage of Piaget. Kids use the skills and abilities they were born with to understand more about the world (such as looking, sucking, grabbing, and listening). In other words, they experience the world and gain knowledge through their senses and motor movements (Cherry, 2018).

An in-depth understanding of the developmental skills and competencies of young Filipino children in the context of the realities of Filipino children in varied age groups is relevant to the appreciation of the Philippine Early Learning and Development Standards (PELDS) and of Early Childhood Care and Development (ECCD) in the Philippines. This may also identify specific psychomotor and cognitive competencies and relevant issues that are unique to the context of Filipino children.

From the above cited literature and theories, the researcher came up with the conceptual framework which is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Paradigm of the Study

Figure 1 shows how the independent variables described in terms of Grade 6 pupils' demographic profile, social and psychological factors and the dependent variables described in terms of Grade 6 pupils' academic performance. Demographic profile described pupils' sex, number of siblings, their 1st quarter general average and socio-economic status. While, social factors described pupils' social influence, social presence, social space, social support, social identity

and social interaction. However, psychological factors described pupils' sense of efficacy, test anxiety, intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation and stress level.

Significance of the Study

The study will be essential and important in the field of education. It will show the correlation of social and psychological factors to pupils' home study setting to their academic performance. Findings and results of this study will ultimately benefit the following:

Pupils. They are the main beneficiaries as respondents of this study. The knowledge acquired through this study will help them gain proper perception that developing home study habits can affect their development psychosocially and academically.

Teachers. Result of this study will remind teachers on their important role in developing the students in terms of skills, psychosocial and academic. Teachers would be aware on the impact of parental involvement on pupils' academic performance.

School Heads. The findings of the study will be beneficial to the school head in managing their respective school. These will provide them a challenge and motivation to enhance the school climate and further improve their instructional materials and physical facilities. The result can be also used as a basis for the school head in doing interventions in strengthening the relationship between parents and the school for the increase of pupils' achievement.

Parents. The findings of the study will be beneficial for parents to be aware on guiding their children and help them in studying in home setting.

Future researchers. The researcher ultimately believes that the results of this study will help the future researchers who have the intention of conducting an in-depth study using other variables.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

The demographic profile of the respondents were limited to their sex and number of siblings. The social factors were limited to social influence, social presence, social space, social interaction, social identity and social support while psychological factors will be limited to sense of self efficacy, test anxiety, intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, and stress level. Grade 6 pupils' academic performance were limited to their general weighted average of their written works and performance tasks during the 1st rating period.

The respondents of this study were limited to the 167 Grade 6 pupils of Liciada Elementary School of Bustos District in Bulacan. It was composed of 4 sections named as Emilio Aguinaldo (SSES), Juan Luna, Julian Felipe and Mariano Ponce.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Research Design

The study utilized descriptive correlational research to describe the relationship between the social and psychological factors that contribute to the home study setting of pupils and their academic performance. Correlational research systematically investigates the relationship among variables and how it significantly affects one another. A researcher should shift from post positivist to constructivist theoretical assumption when this design is adopted in a study (Patalinghug, 2017).

Descriptive correlational research aims to describe a population, situation or phenomenon accurately and systematically. It can answer what, where, when and how questions, but not why questions. A descriptive research design can use a wide variety of research methods to investigate one or more variables (McCombes, 2020).

A t-test was used for evaluating a significant difference in paired measurements among demographic profile, social and psychosocial factors in home-study setting. Pearson correlation coefficient was also used in measuring the degree of linear association between two variables to indicate how or to what extent variables are associated with each other. The findings of this study determined the significant relationship between the social and psychological factors that contribute the home-study setting of pupils and their academic performance. A modified questionnaire for pupils was used as a primary gathering tool.

2.2. Data Gathering Techniques

Questionnaire was used as the main instrument for gathering all the quantitative data needed in the study. The questionnaire was adapted from a research study entitled “Barriers to Online Learning in the Time of COVID-19: A National Survey of Primary and Secondary Students in the Philippines”. However, some modifications were made by the researcher to these questionnaires to suit the present status of Grade 6 pupils. For the qualitative part of the study, five (5) open-ended questions were asked to respondents through personal interview and through phone after the results of the survey questionnaire were determined (Baticolon & Reyes, 2021).

Question wise documents were prepared and query was entertained to explore the word frequency for each of the questions. The data collected was sorted, tallied, tabulated and statistically treated using statistical software for easy computations.

The researcher first sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of Division of Bulacan to conduct the study at Liciada Elementary School. The researcher also asked permission from the school principal in the respondents' school to conduct the study. Following approval, the researcher began collecting data. For ethical purposes and for the sake of the respondents who are below 18 years old, Informed consent was issued to the respondents before the conduct of the study since it was a face-to-face interview. Respondents of the study were informed and oriented on the goal of the research is and provision of the agreement including the potential risks and the possible benefits of taking part in the study and details of alternative options that may benefit the respondents. During the process, the respondents was given the option to ask questions or clarifications. It emphasized also that participation of every respondent is voluntary and that they have the right to withdraw at any time. The content of the informed consent form was written in plain language for clarity and easy to be understand by the respondents. The researcher ensured that that the inform consent form has no misleading or deceptive statements and that the consent form has undergone a critiquing from a competent reviewer or panel of experts. The assurance that signature of each respondent was affixed on the consent form and checked by the researcher.

As for the recording interview, the respondents were informed that the interview was recorded and secured. They were oriented on the type of gadget used and the time allotted for the recording. After that, they were given the opportunity to hear the recording if they desired to do so and was given the option to remove the portion where the respondent deemed to be offensive. The respondent was given the option to repeat the recording process and was given the assurance that the content of the recording will be solely for the study and will not be used for other purpose without prior consent of the them.

The respondents were guaranteed anonymity. All information that obtained, stored electronically, and at no time would participants be identifiable, as there were no identifiable information collected. For the security of collected data, storage, transfer, destruction procedures, data gathered were stored in password-protected computers or files. The recordings stored in a secure location. Upon completion of this research, the recordings were destroyed.

As for paper records, the gathered data was destroyed/disposed in a manner that leaves no possibility for reconstruction of information. Appropriate methods for destroying/disposing of paper includes shredding then cross shredding.

The researcher ensured that after the specific purpose for which the data were gathered and used, the data was no longer retained and be subjected for disposal on August 2023.

2.3. Sampling Procedure

The researcher used total population sampling technique. The total population of grade 6 pupils of Liciada Elementary School served as respondents of the study.

The table 1 below shows the number of male and female pupils who participated in the study.

Table 1 Number of Pupil Respondents

Name of Section	Male	Female	Total
Emilio Aguinaldo	8	24	32
Juan Luna	24	20	44
Julian Felipe	26	20	46
Mariano Ponce	27	18	45
Total	85	82	167

The study utilized 85 male and 82 female pupils that compose 4 sections of Grade 6 pupils. There were total of 167 pupils with parents' respondents.

2.4. Data Analysis Scheme

After all the data were collected, these were organized, tallied, tabulated, and analyze using some statistical tools. Descriptive statistics was used such as frequency distribution and percentage, weighted mean and standard deviation was utilized. It was evaluated using these numerical and descriptive ratings:

Numerical	Descriptive Ratings
4.00-3.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
2.99-2.00	Agree (A)
1.99-1.00	Disagree (D)
0.99-0.01	Strongly Disagree (SD)

2.5. Ethical Consideration

Ethical considerations were ensured throughout the study. The participants were given an informed consent message via the social media platform and was asked to volunteer for the study understanding all the rights of withdrawal and refusal. There was no data sought which could exhibit participants' direct identity like names, telephone numbers, address, area or national identification number.

3. Results

This chapter deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of the data collected and the results of the statistical treatment employed in the study with the purpose of describing the relationship between social and psychological factors in home study setting and Grade 6 pupils' academic performance.

3.1. Demographic Profile

Table 2 presents the respondents' demographic profile in terms of sex, number of siblings, socio-economic status and parent's educational background. It has been shown the respondents' demographic profile with 85 out of 167 or 50.90 % are male respondents while 82 or 49.10 respondents are female. Moreover, there was almost an equal distribution of the respondents' demographic profile in terms of sex. Also, majority of the respondents or 45.51% of the respondents has 1 - 2 number of siblings while there were 15 students or 8.98% who has no siblings at all. Furthermore, there were 77 out of 167 parents or 46.11% has a monthly salary of PhP 10,000.00 and below whereas only 21 parents or 12.57% has a salary between Php 15,001 – PhP 20,000.00. Lastly, most of the parents (father and mother) were high school graduate with 75 or 44.91% for the fathers' highest educational attainment while 56 or 47.31% for mothers' highest educational attainment. Moreover, there were 11 fathers or 6.59% and 5 mothers or 2.99% who were vocational graduates.

It was a rare case to have an almost equal distribution of the respondents' demographic profile in terms of sex. As of 2014, the global sex ratio at birth is estimated at 107 boys to 100 girls (1,000 boys per 934 girls) which was slightly biased towards the male sex. Although sex might affect every facet of society, the importance of its equity in academic research has been historically underappreciated. Some studies find differentiating characteristics between boys and

girls regarding emotional components and unequal maturational development. The differences between boys and girls, regarding social factors, seem to be related to interpersonal factors, where boys are more dominant and calculating and girls are more modest and affectionate. In the same way, educational factors and socialization vary depending on the social and country context; therefore, behaviour according to gender will take place in a particular socio-cultural environment.

Table 2 Respondents' Demographic Profile in terms of Sex, Number of Siblings, Socio-economic Status and Parent's Educational Background

Sex	N		%	
Male	85		50.90	
Female	82		49.10	
TOTAL	167		100.00	
Number of Siblings				
0	15		8.98	
1 - 2	76		45.51	
3 - 4	50		29.94	
5 and up	26		15.57	
TOTAL	167		100.00	
Average Monthly Salary				
P10,000 and below	77	46.11	Poor	
P10,001 – P15,000	35	20.96	Low income	
P15,001 – P20,000	21	12.57	Low income	
P20,001 and above	34	20.36	Low middle income	
TOTAL	167	100.00		
Education	Father	%	Mother	%
Elementary Graduate	34	20.36	27	16.17
High School Graduate	75	44.91	79	47.31
College Graduate	47	28.14	56	33.53
V Vocational	11	6.59	5	2.99
TOTAL	167	100.00	167	100.00

We grew in a Filipino custom where parents were often told by their elders to have two or more children so their kids will learn to be sociable and won't grow up lonely. But parents today were increasingly being shaped by technology and increased access to information about parenting. Becoming a parent is usually a welcomed event, but in some cases, parents' lives are fraught with problems and uncertainty regarding their ability to ensure their child's physical, emotional, or economic well-being.

Socioeconomic status (SES)—indexed via parent educational attainment and family income—is a powerful predictor of children's developmental outcomes. Parents' educational attainment typically drives their income and is often used interchangeably with SES in research. 46.11% of respondents in this study were from "Poor" Filipino social class. By these, parents are bustle around for life and expect little from their kids, and moreover they may put subsistence before children's learning.

In this study, the researcher posits that parent educational attainment provides a foundation that supports children's academic success indirectly through parents' beliefs about and expectations for their children, as well as through the

cognitive stimulation that parents provide in and outside of the home environment. Poverty puts children in disadvantage. Low-income kids start to fall behind in the cognitive development at a young age and have difficulty catching up. They fall behind when they often attend public school education. Consequently, they are more likely to drop-out of high school in their teens, and less likely to get college degree. Thus, they enter adulthood with lower levels of education and this passes on throughout the generation.

Education is an important way for children in low-income families to change their social status. This also means those who yearn for the improvement of their life by studying hard are naive as the bar is raising and the income gap is widening. On that account, government continuously provide fair education opportunities and subsidies in order to cut down the inequality of intergenerational transmission.

3.2. Social Factors in Home-study Setting

Learning environment affects pupils' study habits including people they mingle with. Parents had a direct impact on the education their children received, especially in a home-study setting. Teachers could do the same thing via different learning modalities. Being a coach at any age and reinforcing the value through hardships can empower pupils and ensure that impact is positive. The assessments of the pupils as regards to involvement of social factors in learners' home study setting are manifested in Tables 3 to 7.

3.3. Social Influence

People around the learners had a direct or indirect impact that influences during the home study set-up. Research shows that teachers are the single most important classroom factor in a child's learning achievement. Parents are also accountable at home. But ultimately, teachers are responsible for student learning. The assessments of the respondents regarding their social influence are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3 Description of Social Factors in Home-study Setting in terms of Social Influence

Social Influence	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description
Like me, my friends also have same goals in life.	3.52	0.78	Strongly Agree
I do not go with friends that doesn't give much importance to studying.	2.79	0.86	Agree
My parents have no or little time for me that's why I use my time to just play online games rather than to study.	1.67	0.82	Disagree
Our teacher helps us realize the importance of developing study habits for our academic achievement.	3.83	0.42	Strongly Agree
My peers/friends are my support system to study hard.	3.22	0.75	Agree
Grand Mean	2.95	0.73	Agree

Legend: 1.00 – 1.50 “Strongly Disagree”, 1.51 – 2.50 “Disagree”, 2.51 – 3.50 “Agree” and 3.51 – 4.00 “Strongly Agree”

Table 3 shows the description of social factors in home study setting in terms of social influence with a grand mean of 2.95 with a verbal description of “Agree”. Moreover, 2 of the statements got a verbal description of “Strongly Agree”. Likewise, another 2 statements got a verbal description of “Agree”. However, 1 statement got a verbal description of “Disagree”. Statement 4, “Our teacher helps us realize the importance of developing study habits for our academic achievement” got the highest weighted mean of 3.83 and a standard deviation of 0.42 with a verbal description of “Strongly Agree”. Furthermore, statement 3, “My parents have no or little time for me that's why I use my time to just play online games rather than to study” got the lowest weighted mean of 1.67 and a standard deviation of 0.82 with a verbal description of “Disagree”.

This suggests that social influence in home-study setting affects the learners' goals in studying and their study habits.

This confirms with the study of Younas et al., (2020) as they examined the joint effects of different variables in the home environment on children's development. The study has focused on the relationship between parental variables on children's development, such as parenting style and parenting expectations, which were found to be related to children's

emotion regulation ability. This in turn influences the development of children's social-emotional competence and seek advices from peers and other trusted person.

High quality relationships with teachers and peers in the classroom form the foundation for the development of pupils' academic engagement, achievement, and motivational resilience. Pupils' developed close and supportive relationships when teachers and peers meet their fundamental needs for relatedness, competence and autonomy in school through the provision of warmth and involvement, optimal structure, and autonomy support.

3.4. Social Presence

Family members played vital role in the development of their children. They were encouraged to foster healthy family involvement in every aspect of their children. As children's educations increasingly occur across a range of settings, parents are uniquely positioned to help ensure that these settings best support their children's specific learning needs. The assessments of the respondents regarding their social presence are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4 Description of Social Factors in Home-study Setting in terms of Social Presence

Social Presence	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description
My family relationship affects my studies.	2.50	1.05	Agree
My family members help me in answering my homework.	2.91	0.86	Agree
My siblings explain to me the lessons I don't understand.	2.58	1.09	Agree
I consider studying with family members our bonding moment.	3.20	0.73	Strongly Agree
My parents help me study for upcoming tests/quizzes.	2.96	0.89	Agree
Grand Mean	2.83	0.92	Agree

Legend: 1.00 – 1.50 “Strongly Disagree”, 1.51 – 2.50 “Disagree”, 2.51 – 3.50 “Agree” and 3.51 – 4.00 “Strongly Agree”

As illustrated in Table 4, the grand mean of the social presence as one of the social factors in home study setting was 2.83 which is “Agree”. Four (4) statements got a verbal description of “Agree” and only one (1) statement got “Strongly Agree” as a description. In addition, statement 4, “I consider studying with family members our bonding moment” got the highest weighted mean of 3.20 and a standard deviation of 0.73 with a verbal description of “Strongly Agree” while statement 1, “My family relationship affects my studies” got the lowest weighted mean of 2.50 and a standard deviation of 1.05 with a verbal description of “Agree”.

This indicates that social factors in home-study setting in terms of social presence affects the learners' studies and the support that they got from their parents and siblings may help them in answering the tests/quizzes and even homework.

This confirms with the study of Chung et al., (2020) that parenting style not only has a significant positive direct effect on children's social-emotional development through in-depth research. It can also have indirect effects through the parent-child relationship.

Each child is vulnerable and can either be molded to be successful or made to fail in life. According to the Child and Youth Welfare Code of the Philippines, the child is one of the most important assets of the nation, the promotion and enhancement of the child's life and welfare is also anchored on the moral supervision and support given by his parents or guardians. In order for a child to succeed, parents exert a lot of influence on their child's cognitive development in the early years and thus, the contact between home and school should be maintained, especially during the primary school years. Although family background appears to be a powerful determinant of parental involvement, most parents, if duly encouraged, are able to devote extra time and effort to assisting with their children's education, both in the home and school settings.

3.5. Social Space

When there's an area designated to study when at home, it offers an environment where a pupil can read as loud as possible and feel comfortable about it. For those who prefer to study at home, it is understandable to have a learning space to adapt to their learning style. The assessments of the respondents regarding their social space are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5 Description of Social Factors in Home Study Setting in terms of Social Space

Social Space	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description
I have my own place at home for me to study.	3.04	0.85	Strongly Agree
My siblings keep quiet when they know that I am studying.	2.63	1.03	Agree
My parents give me time to study alone and when I cannot understand the lesson, they give me time to explain it to me.	3.16	0.78	Strongly Agree
My parents explain to me why studying alone is important.	3.20	0.79	Strongly Agree
I understand that finishing study can help me have a comfortable life in the future.	3.75	0.53	Strongly Agree
Grand Mean	3.16	0.80	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00 – 1.50 “Strongly Disagree”, 1.51 – 2.50 “Disagree”, 2.51 – 3.50 “Agree” and 3.51 – 4.00 “Strongly Agree”

Table 5 displays the description of social factors in home study setting in terms of social space got a grand of 3.16 with a verbal description of “Strongly Agree”. Four (4) statements got a “Strongly Agree” and only one (1) statement got “Agree”. Among the statements, statement 5, “I understand that finishing study can help me have a comfortable life in the future” got a highest mean of 3.75 and a standard deviation of 0.53 with a verbal description of “Strongly Agree” whereas statement 2, “My siblings keep quiet when they know that I am studying” got the lowest weighted mean of 2.63 and a standard deviation of 1.03 with a verbal interpretation of “Agree”.

This infers that social space in home-study setting is important to have own place to concentrate in the studies and have personal space.

The result is in consonance with the study of Cuartas (2022) where in his study the family is not only the initial environment to which children are exposed since birth, it also is an important field that influences children's social-emotional development and is the basic unit of interaction with the external environment. Therefore, providing children with a stimulating home environment maximizes their opportunities to develop social-emotional skills on their own.

In the question, “*What do you think is the advantages of studying at home on your learning interest?*”, 28 respondents answered “*I have plenty of time to study*” and 25 of them answered, “*It is easy to understand my lesson because there was no noise and I have peace of mind*”. A good study environment of the children at home can be a significant factor in the success of learning, the lesser the distractions, the higher the focus and information retention. A peaceful study area helped them improve concentration and sharpens their mind. This will also form a habit to a child to be mindful and be well-organized with their belongings. A specific area designated for study creates a boundary for other family members to not make disturbance to the learner while studying. Hence, it will also create a vibe at which the pupil would feel as if they are actually studying, similar in a classroom setting.

3.6. Social Support

Building partnerships between parents and teachers can rely on teachers listening to parents and parents taking the time to understand where teachers are coming from. The assessments of the respondents regarding their social support are summarized in Table 6.

Table 6 Description of Social Factors in Home-study Setting in terms of Social Support

Social Support	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description
I always show my true self to my teachers	3.58	0.59	Strongly Agree
My teacher helps us in difficult/challenging lessons.	3.67	0.58	Strongly Agree
Whenever I come with high marks, I will be given rewards.	3.08	0.85	Agree
My parents give me extra allowance for the things you want to buy.	3.00	0.81	Agree
I allot my allowance for the things I needed in school.	3.24	0.75	Agree
Grand Mean	3.31	0.72	Agree

Legend: 1.00 – 1.50 “Strongly Disagree”, 1.51 – 2.50 “Disagree”, 2.51 – 3.50 “Agree” and 3.51 – 4.00 “Strongly Agree”

As illustrated in Table 6, the grand mean of social factors in home-study setting in terms of social support was 3.31 with a verbal description of “Agree”. Two (2) statements got a verbal description of “Strongly Agree” while three (3) statements got a verbal interpretation of “Agree”. Statement 2, “My teacher helps us in difficult/challenging lessons.” Got the highest mean of 3.67 and a standard deviation of 0.58 with a verbal description of “strongly agree” whereas statement 4, “My parents give me extra allowance for the things you want to buy.” Got the lowest mean of 3.00 and a standard deviation of 0.81 with a verbal description of “Agree”.

This implies that social support plays a vital role in home-study setting as the learner shows their true self to their teachers and teacher support may help them in difficult/challenging lessons.

This confirms the study of Yang et al., (2022) that teacher support had the greatest impact on achievement among students, while it also had a larger influence on student course grades than standardized test scores. The study unraveled the relationship between students’ perceived teacher support and academic achievement as well as to address the role of student engagement, using a meta-analytic approach.

In the question, “What do you think is the best way to boost your learning interest at home?”, 39 respondents answered, it is because they received support from their family.

The best tip for pupils’ academic success is to make sure that parents and teachers are working together as allies. On the home side, parents might have all the things they know about their child, the help they could give them for homework, and their social development with siblings and peers. On the school side of the line, there are all the things their teacher knows about them, the help they’re getting with their school work, and their social development with peers. The information on both sides can be combined to create a fuller understanding of the pupil.

3.7. Social Identity

Childhood is an important period of social development or a person's sense of who they are based upon group affiliations. For some children, the way they feel about themselves and their social identities may contribute to their vulnerability. The assessments of the respondents regarding their social identity are summarized in Table 7.

Table 7 exhibits the description of social factors in home-study setting in terms of social identity with a grand mean of 3.34 with a verbal description of “Strongly Agree”. In Addition, four (4) statements got a verbal description of “Agree” and only one (1) statement got a verbal description of “Strongly Agree”. Furthermore, statement 1 “I learn to believe in myself because of studying” got the highest weighted mean of 3.55 and a standard deviation of 0.64 whereas statement 4 “I always show my true self to my teachers” got the lowest weighted mean and a standard deviation of 3.05 with a verbal description of “Agree”.

The result suggests that social factors in home-study setting in terms of social identity may identify the learner’s strength and weaknesses and use their previous knowledge to understand the new presented topics.

Table 7 Description of Social Factors in Home-study Setting in terms of Social Identity

Social Identity	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description
I learn to believe in myself because of studying.	3.48	0.64	Agree
I started to dream of many things because my teachers inspired me.	3.51	0.61	Strongly Agree
I try to know my own strengths and weaknesses.	3.32	0.70	Agree
I always show my true self to my teachers.	3.05	0.71	Agree
I use the things I know before to help me understand our new lesson.	3.35	0.66	Agree
Grand Mean	3.34	0.66	Agree

Legend: 1.00 – 1.50 “Strongly Disagree”, 1.51 – 2.50 “Disagree”, 2.51 – 3.50 “Agree” and 3.51 – 4.00 “Strongly Agree”

This confirms the study of Demirden (2021) in which he implies that incorporating enhancement and positive distinctiveness motives at the group level and addressing personal motivational and affective processes at the individual level can further refine social identity.

Every individual should know how to perceived various roles in society in relation to others. Whether it is through social position, culture or ethnicity, interests, achievements, or beliefs, children derive a sense of pride, self-worth, and consistency from their social identities. Whether at home or in school, people around these children influenced their social identities and the way they feel about themselves.

3.8. Social Interaction

Good social skills allow kids to interact positively with others and communicate their needs, wants, and feelings effectively. The assessments of the respondents regarding their social interaction are summarized in Table 8.

Table 8 Description of Social Factors in Home-study Setting in terms of Social Interaction

Social Interaction	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description
I learned how to communicate with my friends and teachers through online.	3.37	0.62	Agree
I try to help my peers in understanding the lesson that they find difficult.	3.35	0.58	Agree
I try to fit in with friends that makes me feel comfortable to deal with.	3.12	0.81	Agree
I enjoy learning my lessons even without face-to-face interaction.	2.85	1.02	Agree
I learn to manage my time for study and enjoying moments with friends.	3.39	0.70	Agree
Grand Mean	3.22	0.75	Agree

Legend: 1.00 – 1.50 “Strongly Disagree”, 1.51 – 2.50 “Disagree”, 2.51 – 3.50 “Agree” and 3.51 – 4.00 “Strongly Agree”

As shown in Table 8, the grand mean of the social factors in home-study setting in terms of social interaction was 3.22 with a verbal description of “Agree”. It is noticeable from the table that five (5) of the statements got a verbal description of “Agree”. Statement 5 “I learn to manage my time for study and enjoying moments with friends” got the highest weighted mean of 3.39 and a standard deviation of 0.70 with a verbal description of “Agree” while statement 4 “I enjoy learning my lessons even without face-to-face interaction” got a verbal description of “Agree” with a weighted mean of 2.85 and a standard deviation of 1.02.

Based from the result, social interaction plays a vital role in home-study setting as the learners enjoy time studying with their friends and help their peers to understand the lessons that they find difficult.

In conformity with the present findings, Eriksen et al., (2019) study stated that the most challenging factors to students in becoming an effective peer coach were developing their ability to effectively listen to their peers and the fear associated with asking their partner challenging or probing questions. Rather than listening, students found themselves interjecting their opinions, offering advice, talking about themselves, or relating what their partners were saying to their own lives, if only in their minds. They found the most effective aspects of students' peer coaching in supporting peers' leadership development were being nonjudgmental, listening, accountability, and asking questions.

It was amazing how much youngsters learn in the first few years of their life. They were able to learn most of this from observing. But social interaction is one thing that they learned from by experiencing it for themselves. There was a lot that can be learned from social interaction, and children learned these things from observing others interacting with each other. When they are young, they will be able to learn from social experiences and develop different social skills based on those interactions. As they get older, it was hard to learn from interaction with others and change our ways. A child that learned how to interact with others properly will have an easier time in social settings throughout the rest of their lives.

3.9. Psychological Factors in Home-study Setting

These refer to the psychological determinants that affect pupils' home-study setting. Parents should have a deeper understanding that the impact of home-study on family processes is essential if the psychological wellbeing of families is to be protected and supported during challenging times such as health-related disasters.

The assessments of the pupils as regards to involvement of psychological factors in learners' home study setting are manifested in Tables 9 to 13.

3.10. Sense of Self-efficacy

The belief in one's own ability to do something, find resources, gain knowledge and problem-solving is the key to understanding own self-efficacy. The assessments of the respondents regarding their sense of self-efficacy are summarized in Table 9.

Table 9 Description of Psychological Factors through Home-study Setting in terms of Sense of Self-efficacy

Sense of Self-efficacy	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description
I enjoy playing online games more than studying my lessons.	1.88	0.80	Agree
Our family's current situation inspires me to study harder.	3.34	0.69	Agree
I can still study my lessons even I'm alone.	3.17	0.69	Agree
I finish my modules with little or no help from my parents and siblings.	3.01	0.65	Agree
I review my lessons for upcoming quizzes or tests alone.	3.10	0.81	Agree
Grand Mean	2.90	0.73	Agree

Legend: 1.00 – 1.50 “Strongly Disagree”, 1.51 – 2.50 “Disagree”, 2.51 – 3.50 “Agree” and 3.51 – 4.00 “Strongly Agree”

Table 9 shows the description of psychological factors through home-study setting in terms of sense of self-efficacy got a grand mean of 2.90 with a verbal description of “Agree”. All of the five (5) statements got a verbal description of “Agree”. In addition, statement 2 “Our family's current situation inspires me to study harder.” got the highest weighted mean of 3.34 and a standard deviation of 0.69 with a verbal description of “Agree” whereas the lowest weighted mean was 1.88 and a standard deviation of 0.80 from statement 1 “I enjoy playing online games more than studying my lessons” with a verbal description of “Disagree”.

The result shows that the learners in terms of sense of self-efficacy as a psychological factor through home study setting that students can learn the lessons alone and can finish the worktext with or without the help of the family members.

The study is in consonance with the result of Mamolo (2022) which implies the improvement of online learning processes, emphasizing government projects for faster internet connectivity helps the students to study on their own. Also, the emphasis on engaging classroom activities, must be established to improved learners' motivation and self-efficacy and decreasing anxiety.

In the question, *“What do you think is the best way to boost your learning interest at home?”*, 39 respondents answered, they need to give more time to study hard for their future. The belief in one's own ability to succeed plays a role in how a person think, how he act, and how he feel about one's existence. The respondents already knew what goals are they going to pursue, how they will accomplish those goals, and how they will reflect upon their own performance.

3.11. Test Anxiety

Tests and exams in school inform teachers, parents, and pupils themselves about their academic progress and potential future pathways. But like any situation in which a person's performance was being evaluated, the outcomes may feel very significant. So exams have the potential to be stressful. The assessments of the respondents regarding their test anxiety are summarized in Table 10.

Table 10 Description of Psychological Factors through Home-study Setting in terms of Test Anxiety

Sense of Test Anxiety	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description
During a test, I feel nervous when the teacher next to me thus making me no longer answer the question.	2.56	0.83	Agree
I often cry after a test thinking how badly I have done.	2.13	0.97	Disagree
Before I take the test, I can feel that I might fail it.	2.65	0.87	Agree
I'm constantly restless throughout the test.	2.40	0.80	Disagree
My mind goes blank during the test even I studied beforehand.	2.56	0.85	Agree
Grand Mean	2.46	0.86	Disagree

Legend: 1.00 – 1.50 “Strongly Disagree”, 1.51 – 2.50 “Disagree”, 2.51 – 3.50 “Agree” and 3.51 – 4.00 “Strongly Agree”

As reflected in table 10, the description of psychological factors through home-study setting in terms of test anxiety got a grand mean of 2.46 with a verbal description of “Disagree”. Moreover, three (3) out of five (5) statements got a verbal interpretation of “Agree” and two (2) statements got a verbal interpretation of “Disagree”. Statement 3, “Before I take the test, I can feel that I might fail it” got the highest mean of 2.65 and a standard deviation of 0.87 with a verbal description of “Agree” while statement 2, “I often cry after a test thinking how badly I have done” got the lowest mean of 2.13 and a standard deviation of 0.97 with a verbal description of “Disagree”.

Based from the result, students tend to goes blank during examination even they studied the lessons before and they feel nervous when the teacher is beside them.

This confirms in an article by Andrillon et al., (2021) that “electroencephalogram” were responsible in the occurrence of the sleep markers that predict instances of mind wandering and mind blanking that leads to behavioral errors during a task. Mind wandering and mind blanking are everyday-life phenomena that can have dramatic consequences if they occur at the wrong moment. They increase when we get tired, after a long day, for example, or a task demanding deep focus, such as driving a car, or during exams, or even in the middle of a presentation. The lapse of memory is caused by extreme agitation or stress that constricts our thinking. Even the mere fact that you are scared of experiencing a memory lapse can be a trigger causing additional exam anxiety.

It is not unusual for students of all ages to feel nervous before an exam, test, or quiz. However, when that fear becomes overwhelming and affects a person's test performance, they may have test anxiety that would lead to underachievement in an academic setting. However, by learning about coping skills and finding ones that work for them, people may be able to calm their anxiety and potentially improve their academic outcomes.

3.12. Intrinsic Motivation

People are more motivated when they pursue goals with personal meaning and when attaining the goal is possible but not necessarily certain. These goals may also relate to self-esteem when performance feedback is available. The assessments of the respondents regarding their intrinsic motivation are summarized in Table 11

Table 11 Description of Psychological Factors through Home-study Setting in terms of Intrinsic Motivation

Intrinsic Motivation	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description
Whenever I come with low marks, I will not be given any punishments.	2.89	0.78	Agree
My parents have no or little time for me that's why I use my time to just play online games rather than to study.	1.82	0.87	Disagree
I sometimes skip homework/schoolwork.	1.98	0.82	Disagree
I think having study habits enhances my learning skills.	3.21	0.67	Agree
I enjoy playing online games more than studying my lessons.	1.66	0.70	Disagree
Grand Mean	2.31	0.77	Disagree

Legend: 1.00 – 1.50 “Strongly Disagree”, 1.51 – 2.50 “Disagree”, 2.51 – 3.50 “Agree” and 3.51 – 4.00 “Strongly Agree”

Table 11 displays the description of psychological factors through home-study setting in terms of intrinsic motivation got a grand mean of 2.31 with a verbal description of “Disagree”. Moreover, three (3) out of five (5) statements got a verbal description of “Disagree” and two (2) statements got a verbal description of “Agree”. Statement 4, “I think having study habits enhances my learning skills” got the highest mean of 3.21 and a standard deviation of 0.67 with a verbal description of “Agree” whereas statement 5, “I enjoy playing online games more than studying my lessons” got the lowest mean of 1.66 and a standard deviation of 0.70 with a verbal description of “Disagree”.

As shown in the result, students agreed that whenever they got low grades/marks, they will not be punished but rather encourage them to do well on the next exams. Moreover, students think that having a good study habit may enhance their learning skills.

This is in consonance with the study of Kumar (2019) where in students with good study habits get higher grades. The results of studies have shown that students' possession of study habits help them have high motivation for learning, take more time to learn, have positive attitudes towards learning and feel more successful.

In the question, “*What do you think is the best way to boost your learning interest at home?*”, only 8 respondents answered receiving rewards for their achievement do really help them to become motivated in their studies, while 16 of them answered “*Make a to-do-list to reach goals*”. Rather than relying on grades as external motivators, teachers can help pupils develop intrinsic motivation by providing opportunities for autonomy and building their sense of competence. To support students' autonomy, teachers do encourage them to set their own learning objectives, contribute to course material, and use learning techniques that work best for them.

3.13. Extrinsic Motivation

Pupils' motivation for some was driven by rewards, while others continue to perform a task even though it might not be in and of itself rewarding. The assessments of the respondents regarding their extrinsic motivation are summarized in Table 12.

As below seen in table 12, the grand mean for psychological factors through home-study setting in terms of extrinsic motivation was 3.50 with a verbal interpretation of “Agree”. Also, three (3) out of five (5) statements got a verbal interpretation of “Strongly Agree” while two (2) statements got a verbal interpretation of “Agree”. Moreover, statement 2, “Our teacher helps us to develop good study habits” got the highest mean of 3.66 and a standard deviation of 0.54 with a verbal description of “Strongly Agree” while statement 3, “My circle of friends and family members help me understand our new lesson” got the lowest mean of 3.19 and a standard deviation of 0.77 with a verbal description of “Agree”.

Table 12 Description of Psychological Factors through Home-study Setting in terms of Extrinsic Motivation

Sense of Extrinsic Motivation	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description
Our teacher inspires me to study harder.	3.63	0.59	Strongly Agree
Our teacher helps us to develop good study habits.	3.66	0.54	Strongly Agree
My circle of friends and family members help me understand our new lesson.	3.19	0.77	Agree
Our teacher reviews the previous lesson first before jumping into a new one.	3.60	0.59	Strongly Agree
Our teacher provides remediation for those who had difficulty in learning the new lesson.	3.40	0.68	Agree
Grand Mean	3.50	0.63	Agree

Legend: 1.00 – 1.50 “Strongly Disagree”, 1.51 – 2.50 “Disagree”, 2.51 – 3.50 “Agree” and 3.51 – 4.00 “Strongly Agree”

As the result says, that students were inspired by their teachers to do a good study habits and study hard to attain higher marks in the examination.

This confirms the study of Boholano et al., (2021) that teachers are concern with students’ learning. The study suggested that when grading learners in the new normal, schools should change the ways they use assessment scales from “quantitative to qualitative “ for the student to attain higher marks in any kind of classroom assessment. The study found that teachers remained optimistic about pursuing digital literacy to develop effective and efficient remote teaching skills to ensure that no students will left behind.

In today’s fast-paced world, engaging pupils was a major challenge for teachers. Oftentimes, it’s all about finding the proper motivation. In the classroom, just as in real life, there are many things we have to do that, if given the choice, we would not. Sometimes the right incentive serves as the hook that gets pupils invested in learning. Pupils choose behaviors not because they enjoy them or find them satisfying, but in order to get something in return or avoid an adverse outcome.

3.14. Stress level

Feelings of stress are a part of ones’ life. It is simply the body’s response to changes that create taxing demands. Pupils tend to feel stress specially when they have to do something but were unprepared. The assessments of the respondents regarding their stress level are summarized in Table 13

Table 13 Description of Psychological Factors through Home-study Setting in terms of Stress Level

Sense of Stress Level	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description
I feel nauseated when I’m in school.	1.84	0.82	Disagree
When I am in school, I am thinking to get the time fly so fast so I can go home.	2.51	0.81	Agree
I don’t feel comfortable with my classmates and teachers.	1.65	0.94	Disagree
I am not happy when I am in school.	1.55	0.77	Disagree
I feel so stress that I don’t want weekends to finish.	1.98	0.83	Disagree
Grand Mean	1.90	0.83	Disagree

Legend: 1.00 – 1.50 “Strongly Disagree”, 1.51 – 2.50 “Disagree”, 2.51 – 3.50 “Agree” and 3.51 – 4.00 “Strongly Agree”

Table 13 illustrates the description of psychological factors through home-study setting in terms of stress level with a grand mean of 1.90 with a verbal description of “disagree”. meanwhile, only one (1) statement got a verbal description of “Agree” while four (4) statements got verbal description of “Disagree”. Statement 2, “When I am in school, I am

thinking to get the time fly so fast so I can go home” got the highest mean of 2.51 and a standard deviation of 0.81 with a verbal description of “Agree” whereas statement 4, “I am not happy when I am in school” got the lowest mean of 1.55 and a standard deviation of 0.77 with a verbal description of “Disagree”.

As the result suggest, students were stress whenever they were at school and thinking that time would fly fast to get home and they don’t feel comfortable with their teachers and classmates at school.

This is in consonance with the study of Rusticus et al.,(2023) the learning environment comprises the psychological, social, cultural and physical setting in which learning occurs and has an influence on student motivation and success. The study increases the understanding of learning environment by incorporating data collected from both students and faculty working in the same context. Across both groups, we identified important aspects of the learning environment as being high levels of engagement and motivation, a positive emotional climate, support among peers, strong faculty–student relationships, meaningful experiences, and small class sizes. If the students identified negative aspects of the learning environment, such as certain characteristics of group work and struggles with work–life balance, they tend to leave the learning environment at all cost.

In the qualitative part question, “*Did you ever worry about your grade’s stressor?*”, 97 respondents answered yes. They overcome this by asking for help from my classmates, teacher, and even family members. If they have free time, they study more and review their notes specially in Math, English and Science. The understanding of how stress affects primary school children’s attention and learning has developed rapidly. Children experienced differing levels of stressors (factors that cause stress) in their environments, and that this can influence how they respond to new stressors when they occur in educational contexts.

3.15. Academic Achievement

In this part of the study, the academic achievement of the learners which is measured in terms of their grades in 1st quarter of school year 2022-2023 were manifested in Table 14.

Table 14 Academic Achievement of Respondents for 1st Quarter of School Year 2022 – 2023

General Average	N	%
98-100	0	0.00
95-97	0	0.00
90-94	21	12.57
85-89	56	33.53
80-84	76	45.51
75-79	14	8.38
TOTAL	167	100.00

As exhibited in Table 14, 76 out of 167 students were on the bracket of 80-84 while only 14 students were on the bracket of 75-79.

In accordance to the present findings, Lettau (2021) in her research summarized that a positive relationship between competencies and children’s well-being are not controlled for individual and family-related background characteristics, such as intelligence and socioeconomic background. These differences in the effect of children’s academic competence levels on their life satisfaction, taking into account the school track attended, sensitivity analyses also show differences between boys and girls. While higher mathematical competencies are negatively associated with life satisfaction for boys, the effect is the opposite for girls. This could indicate gender-related consequences of higher achievement in children’s everyday experiences, as high levels of mathematical competencies are assumed to have a different meaning for boys and girls. It is hypothesized, that higher levels of competence represent higher levels of school engagement, which is more likely to be associated with typical female gender roles.

In the qualitative question, “*During the first quarter of this school year, what is the biggest challenge that you encounter after two years of studying from your chosen modality?*”, 37 respondents answered, “*I need to wake up very early.*” Since it was their face-to-face class after how many years of pandemic, pupils were still coping up with the adjustment made

by the transition from home-based learning set-up to in person studying. Parents were also adjusting as they go back to their normal work. Limited time was given to their children at home, and teaching them was not priority. Teachers delivered lessons in a comfortable learning environment without putting lesson excessiveness to avoid pressure that may lead to absenteeism or anxiety since 34 respondents answered, *I have difficulty to understand my lesson*". Most of the respondents were contented to their first quarter general average grade with a rating of "Satisfactorily" and not feel any pressure to do well at school. This was agreed by 22 respondents who answered, *"I have difficulty in answering test/quizzes"*, and *"I can't ask help from my parents whenever I want to"*

Table 15 Test of Significant Difference among Demographic Profile, Social and Psychological Factors in Home-study Setting

		r-value	p-value	Verbal Description	Decision
Sex	Social Factor	0.032	0.679	Not Significant	Accept
	Psychological Factor	0.052	0.505	Not Significant	Accept
Number of Siblings	Social Factor	-0.197	0.011	Significant	Reject
	Psychological Factor	-0.045	0.560	Not Significant	Accept
Socioeconomic Status	Social Factor	0.277	0.000	Significant	Reject
	Psychological Factor	-0.119	0.125	Not Significant	Accept
Father's Educational Background	Social Factor	0.034	0.659	Not Significant	Accept
	Psychological Factor	-0.080	0.303	Not Significant	Accept
Mother's Educational Background	Social Factor	-0.054	0.0.489	Not Significant	Accept
	Psychological Factor	-0.042	0.591	Not Significant	Accept
Social Factor	Psychological Factor	-0.025	0.745	Not Significant	Accept

Legend: <0.05 = significant

Table 15 shows the test of Significant Difference among Demographic Profile, Social and Psychological Factors in Home Study Setting. Moreover, number of siblings and socio-economic status has a significant difference between pupils' demographic profile and social factor in home study setting with p-values 0.011 and 0.000 which is less than the level of significance at 0.05, therefore, reject the null hypothesis. Furthermore, sex, father and mother educational background have no significant difference between pupils' demographic profile and social factor with p-values greater than 0.05 level of significance, therefore, do not reject the null hypothesis. The hypothesis "There is no significant difference among demographic profile, social and psychological factors in home study setting of respondents" was accepted since the result proves that no significant relationship with p-values greater than the level of significance at 0.05. Also, Social and Psychological factors in home study setting have no significant difference with p-value greater than 0.05 level of significance, therefore, the hypothesis was accepted.

The result was supported by the study of McLean et al., (2022) that recognizing and acknowledging the challenges of home-study is important, and should be included in . instrumental support is needed for those involved in home-schooling, as perceived levels of support is associated with improved outcomes. Proactive planning by schools to support parents may promote better outcomes and improved home-study experiences for students.

In this study, the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of number of siblings and socio-economic status has significant relationship to social factors in home-study setting. As educational attainment is usually viewed as a prerequisite for occupational success, much research has focused on how parental socio-economic status (SES) influences educational attainment processes. Family SES in terms of parents' education and income actually affect children's outcomes as it emphasizes family economic resources. The family's economic condition determines how much parents can invest in their children's education and development. The more children do a family have; the bigger resources were needed for the education. If the parents cannot longer sustain their children's need, they stopped studying and look for alternative ways to earn money even at young age.

Education holds the key to a society's development and economic growth and for individuals, education is a major social determinant of almost all aspects of life. Hence, the unequal distribution of education across different members in a

society remains one of the most consequential sources of social inequality—indeed it is the main mechanism through which parents transmit their social advantages or disadvantages to children intergenerationally.

3.16. Relationship among Social and Psychological Factors in Home-study Setting and Respondents' Academic Achievement

Social factor in Home-study setting and Respondents' Academic Achievement has a significant relationship with p-value of 0.001 which was less than the level of significance at 0.05. Therefore, reject the null hypothesis. On the other hand, Psychological factor in home study setting and Respondents' Academic Achievement has no significant relationship with p-value 0.220 which was greater than the level of significance at 0.05, therefore, do not reject the null hypothesis.

The result is in consonance with the study of Usán (2021) where findings are consistent with previous studies in which motivational and social factors, as opposed to emotional factors, were related to academic achievement. The study concludes that academic achievement is closely related to motivational and social factors and, to a lesser extent, to emotional factors. In addition, geographical area plays a moderating role in these factors while age only plays a role in social factors. These results highlight the importance of motivational and social factors regarding academic achievement. In addition, along with the moderating effect of age, that of geographical area emerges strongly given the diversity of contexts studied. Our results highlight the importance that these factors have on academic performance and, therefore, the need to design school plans that address the correct development of these variables.

Prior studies suggest that both psychological and social factors influence ones' academic performance. However, only a few studies considered the unique contribution of these factors or tested their influences on pupils' current outcomes. Moreover, fewer such studies have focused on low-income middle students' academic performance. This limits the ability of the researcher to understand some important issues, such as whether the importance of the social and psychological factors changes over. In this study, the hypothesis has been split into two results. Only social factors have significant relationship to academic performance through home-study setting as measured in Grade 6 pupils were significantly predictive of their general average as per 1st quarter of school year.

4. Discussion

This study determined the relationship between among social and psychological factors in home study setting, and pupils' academic achievement of Grade 6 pupils in Liciada Elementary School during the first quarter of School Year 2022-2023.

Using the procedures described in the preceding chapter, the answers to the problems raised in this study were ascertained and summarized as follows: Findings revealed that almost half of the parents were able to obtain high school degree; employed; earned Php10, 000 and below per month; and have 1 to 2 independent children.

Highly significant relation was found between social factors in home studying and pupils' academic achievement. Social factors had a significant role in cognitive development among children. Children live with their own parents, and they interact with their peers and teachers; all of these had a great deal of influence on pupils' level of thinking and understanding to account for social factors and cultural contexts in cognitive development studies.

Pupils' social factors in home study setting in terms of social influence affects the learners' goals in studying and their study habits. The result stated that the teacher helps them realize the importance of developing study habits for their academic achievement. Social presence affects the learners' studies and the support that they got from their parents and siblings may help them in answering the tests/quizzes and even homework. Social space in home study setting is important so they have their own place to concentrate in the studies and having personal space gave them time to focus and concentrate. Social support plays a vital role in home study setting as the learner shows their true self to their teachers and teacher support may help them in difficult/challenging lessons. Social identity helps the learners identify their strength and weaknesses and use their previous knowledge to understand the new presented topics. Whereas, social interaction plays a vital role in home study setting as the learners enjoy time studying with their friends and help their peers to understand the lessons that they find difficult.

On the other hand, the result of psychological factor through home-study setting has no direct impact to pupils' academic achievement. In terms of sense of self-efficacy, study shows that the pupils can learn the lessons alone and can finish the worktext with or without the help of the family members. As for the test anxiety, pupils naturally tend to go blank during examination even they studied the lessons before because they feel nervous when the teacher is beside them. For pupils' intrinsic motivation, they agreed that whenever they got low grades/marks, they will not be punished but

rather encourage them to do well on the next exams. Teachers are the primary source of their extrinsic motivation. Pupils were inspired by their teachers to do a good study habits and study hard to attain higher marks in the examination. They encourage their pupils to think that having a good study habit may enhance their learning skills. But when they were stress, they think of that time would fly fast to get home specially when they don't feel comfortable with their teachers and classmates at school.

5. Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that social factors in home study setting and respondents' academic achievement has a significant relationship. The number of siblings and socio-economic status has a significant difference between students' demographic profile and social factor in home study setting. On the other hand, psychological factor in home study setting and respondents' academic achievement has no significant relationship.

Recommendations

In light of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are hereby presented:

- For parents, play-based activity will be given at home to support positive family relationships and promote learning. Give time to teach your children and let them feel your love and support.
- For parents and teachers, encouragement and motivation inside school or at home will help pupils boost their eagerness to learn. By giving a compliment and rewards, this rings true to all people regardless of their status, sex or age.
- For school head, additional programs for improving pupils' psychosocial development is highly recommended. By providing problem-focused coping style it will help them change or eliminate the source of their stress or anxiety in school or even at home.
- For future researchers, further research along this line could be conducted in the intermediate learners from different school to further validate the significance of the variables under study to social and psychological factors.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of ethical approval

The present research work does not contain any studies performed on animals/humans subjects by any of the authors'.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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